

RELATIONSHIP OF TYPES OF PAPILLARY PATTERNS OF FINGERS AND TOES IN THE ASPECT OF THE POSSIBILITY OF ESTABLISHING LIMBS BELONGING TO ONE CORPSE DURING FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION OF FRAGMENTED CORDS

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ANNOTATION

The article is devoted to solving an urgent problem of forensic medicine - the search for diagnostic markers of the common origin of biological objects, which is important in the practice of forensic medical examination of corpses fragmented during an explosion.

Purpose of the study. The study is based on dermatoglyphic research method, with the help of which the relationship between the papillary patterns of the fingers and toes is studied.

Materials and methods of research.

The research materials were the fingerprints and toes of 169 people (20 prints for each subject, 3380 prints in total). Persons of both sexes, aged from 16 to 83 years, of Caucasian race, without externally noticeable congenital diseases and markers of pathological dermatoglyphics, were examined.

Variation statistics methods were used to process the obtained data. To assess the strength of the relationship between the papillary patterns of individual fingers and the limbs as a whole (expressed by the number of deltas), correlation analysis (Pearson) was used.

Results of the study and their discussions.

At the first stage of the study, we studied combinations of types of papillary patterns of the fingers and toes of the same side (with the so-called homolateral comparison). It was found that on the right side, out of five types of patterns on the thumbs and five types of patterns on the big toes, 25 different combinations could theoretically occur. In the sample of "our own" there were actually 12. The most common: "Lu-Lf" ($43.2 \pm 3.8\%$), "W-Lf" ($29.0 \pm 3.5\%$) and "WW" ($9, 5 \pm 2.3\%$). In the sample, composed of hands and feet belonging to different individuals (obtained by randomly rearranging the identifiers of the individuals being examined), 16 combinations were found (an additional four combinations: "A-Lt", "Lu-Lw", "Lw-A" and "Lw-Lt"). A comparison of the frequency of occurrence of characteristic combinations showed (Table 1) that only five combinations had a statistically significant level of differences in the samples of "us" and "strangers" (at the $p < 0.05$ level). Of these, the combinations "Lu-Lf" and "W-Lf" are typical for "friends", and "Lu-Lt", "Lu-W" and "W-Lt" for strangers. The multiplicity of differences ranges from two to 14 units. Calculations regarding the characteristics of the left side did not reveal any informative combinations.

At the second stage of the study, with a heterolateral comparison of the types of papillary patterns of the big toes of the right hand and big toes of the left foot, it was established that there was a statistically significant level of differences in the samples of "friends" and "foes" (at the $p < 0.05$ level) only two combinations: "WW" (characteristic of "friends") and "Lu-W" (characteristic of "strangers"). In the opposite version of the comparison - for the types of

papillary patterns of the big toes of the left hand and the big toes of the right foot - no informative characteristic combinations were found.

Conclusions. For the first time, a comprehensive study of all possible combinations and relationships of the types of papillary patterns of the fingers and toes was carried out, in various comparison options: homo- and heterolateral, homo- and heteroradial.

It has been established that informative (from the point of view of the possibility of establishing a common origin) combinations of pattern types are rare and are mainly observed on the thumbs, more often with homolateral comparison. For practical purposes, it should be recommended to analyze combinations of the types of papillary patterns of the thumbs of the right hand and the right foot, as well as the difference in the delta index values of the papillary patterns of the fingers of one (any) hand and one (any) foot.

The bilateral relationship between the types of papillary patterns is almost twice as strong as their homo- and heterolateral relationship (at the same time, the bilateral relationship between homologous toes is stronger than that of fingers) and has the greatest prospects for use in forensic medical practice.

References:

1. Akopov V.I., Bozhchenko A.P., Shcherbakov V.V., Yunusova O.M. and others. Organizational and scientific issues of medical and forensic identification of an unidentified corpse using dermatoglyphics of fingers and toes // Problematic issues of forensic medical examination . - 2001. - P. 5-9.
2. Bozhchenko A.P., Gomon A.A., Ismailov M.T. Racial diagnostic features of foot dermatoglyphics // Health and education in the 21st century. - 2018. - No. 1 (20). - pp. 181-186.
3. Bozhchenko A.P., Kapustin E.V. Bilateral symmetry of palmoglyphic features as a criterion for palms belonging to one person // Forensic examination. - 2019. - No. 1. - P. 76-90.
4. Bozhchenko A.P., Teplov K.V., Gugin I.V. Group polymorphism and variability of dermatoglyphic characters of fingers and toes; comparative characteristics // Forensic medical examination. - 2014. - No. 4. - P. 34-40.
5. Maksimishina Yu.V. Papillary patterns of the toes and soles in comparison with the patterns of the fingers and palms / Proceedings on forensic medicine and border areas. - M., 1965. - P. 227-228.
6. Taraskaev S.A. On the issue of classification of papillary patterns on the nail phalanges of the toes of the right and left feet // Business in law . - 2009. - No. 1. - P. 205-207.
7. Fandeeva O.M. Study of dermatoglyphic signs of toes as characteristics of genetic relatedness in relation to forensic identification examinations: abstract . discand. honey _ n auk. - M., 2002. - 16 p.